

A case study of primary progressive aphasia and its impact on foreign language proficiency compared to L1

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Abstract

This study was designed to examine the impact of progressive aphasia on the multilingual brain. The main objective was to verify the status of the first acquired language (L1; Tunisian Arabic) against the status of a lately acquired foreign language (L2; English). The study reports on the case of an elderly Tunisian patient presenting with a diagnosis of primary progressive aphasia caused by the onset of the Alzheimer disease. A set of picture-naming tasks was administered to the patient to examine his naming aptitude in L1 and L2 for the semantic categories of : Letters, Numbers, Plants, Animals, Body parts, Colors and Clothes. The case's responses in L1 and L2 were qualitatively analysed and compared. Dissociation in performance was reported within the same linguistic system (L1/L2) as well as between both systems (L1 vs. L2) with L2 being the most affected after the neurodegenerative damage. An account was found in category-specificity of semantic knowledge.

A difference in the grammatical gender of nouns between TA and English was suggested as a possible factor affecting the patient's performance as well. The reported dissociations between L1 and L2 suggested their segregation at a cognitive level. This anatomical segregation could have important implications for the clinical and the teaching fields. Clinically, identifying the most deficient language after brain damage should direct the language pathologist towards treating it with a special care offering a

better prognosis for the weaknesses. Pedagogically, foreign language teaching methods should focus on fortifying the anatomic segregation between languages while enhancing authenticity in the L2 learning environment. This will hopefully reduce the occurrence of negative language transfer from L1 to L2.

Key words: categorical effect of semantic knowledge, multilingual brain, primary progressive aphasia

1. Introduction

Language pathology can be caused by a wide array of circumstances that are mostly split between neurological and psychological. The neurological damage leading to the linguistic defect can be acute or progressive. The progressive aspect of a language trouble is mainly caused by neurodegenerative diseases with Alzheimer being the most known type of these. One leading syndrome of Alzheimer is a language trouble referred to as primary progressive aphasia where language capacities degenerate progressively due to brain damage affecting language areas. The following section is devoted to the explanation of this syndrome.

1.1. Primary progressive aphasia

Primary progressive aphasia (PPA) is defined as “a neurodegenerative disorder with language impairment as the primary feature” (Rohrer et al., 2012, p. 744). Thus, opposed to other types of aphasias mainly emanating from acute and focal brain damage, primary progressive aphasia is caused by a progressive neurodegenerative type of damage which is rather diffuse. While the acute types of aphasias may have a good prognostic over a long period of time, progressive aphasia is rather evolving towards a more devastating state of a linguistic defect with usually no hope for a positive reversal. However, language rehabilitation still can play a great role in supporting patients with several compensatory strategies to help them cope with the daily linguistic struggle in the communication task. Zanini et al. (2011) described PPA to be “a clinical syndrome characterized by progressive language loss without significant general cognitive or motor decline for at least 2 years after the appearance of linguistic impairment” (p. 535). It is generally accepted that PPA has three subtypes: “progressive nonfluent aphasia (PNFA), semantic dementia (SD) and logopenic/phonological aphasia (LPA)” (Rohrer et al., 2012, p. 744). Of the previously mentioned subtypes, LPA is “most commonly associated with Alzheimer's disease (AD) pathology” (Rohrer et al., 2012, p. 744).

The PPA is a clinical condition which could affect a monolingual brain as well as a bilingual or a multilingual one. Though, the incidence and prevalence of the PPA affecting a multilingual brain have been increasing in response to societal changes. Addressing aphasia in the context of the multilingual brain is not without merit as will be explained in the following.

1.2. Aphasia and the multilingual brain

In the recent decades, learning different languages is more and more appealing to the curriculum designers since the world is constantly growing into a compacted space. In response to the worldwide urge to learn languages to be well connected and well integrated, “language impairment in multilingual persons is likely to become a frequent clinical challenge” (Lekoubou et al., 2015, p. 1). In point of fact, “since most people in the world know more than one language, bilingual aphasia is an important line of research in clinical and theoretical neurolinguistics” (Fabbro, 2001, p. 201). Indeed, multilingualism opens new horizons for the understanding of the relationship between brain and language. Lekoubou et al. (2015) affirm that “multilingual patients with acquired speech problems may present clinical nuances that underscore the relationship between anatomical lesions and subtypes of language deficits, both in the first as well as in their second languages” (p. 1).

It is accepted that bilingual aphasia “generally affects both languages”¹(Tschirren et al., 2011, p. 238). Interestingly, several researches focused on which language is the most defective in case of multilingual brain damage affecting language areas (e.g. Fabbro, 2001; Tschirren et al., 2011). Research on this issue presented controversial results that emerged even within the same group of study (e.g. Fabbro, 2001). Fabbro

¹ First and second languages

(2001) investigated language recovery of 20 bilingual Friulian-Italian aphasics and found that “thirteen patients (65%) showed a similar impairment in both languages (parallel recovery), four patients (20%) showed a greater impairment of L2, while three patients (15%) showed a greater impairment of L1” (p. 201). Comparing the effect of neurodegenerative damage on L1 and L2 could also allow verifying hypotheses about the neural representation of languages in the bilingual brain.

1.3. The current study

In the current study, a set of denomination tasks is applied to an individual case with progressive aphasia to draw inferences regarding the effect of language impairment on L1 and L2. Data was collected through one extended session of testing where breaks were offered when the patient needed. The type and prevalence of errors were analysed comparing L1 and L2 across the patient’s response to the tested items belonging to several semantic categories. The objective was to understand whether errors manifest differently in the separate language systems.

Another aim was to explore whether specific errors are typical to one specific language in order to determine whether production is constrained by a typically organized lexico-semantic processing system that distinguished between L1 and L2 thus reflecting some language-specific cognitive processes. In the following, the methodology which was used will be thoroughly explained.

2. Methods

2.1. Description of the case study

The case of study, GT, is an elderly right-handed Tunisian man, aged 73 years, and diagnosed with Alzheimer at the age of 72. He retired from a high qualified post at the Ministry of agriculture, 10 years ago. He was an out-patient of the CHU Razi (Mannouba hospital, Tunisia) and was mainly suffering from amnesia that affected more specifically his episodic memory. His medical records indicated several ancient right ischemic lesions as

well as recent lesions at the level of the left hippocampus confirmed by MRI². His MMS³ score downgraded from 26/30 the day of admission to 22/30 within a short period suggesting a fast decay of memory. When examined by a language pathologist, deficient access to the lexical system was revealed. His spatial awareness was reserved while his temporal awareness was seriously altered. GT used to be a good English speaker since he lived several years in America. His premorbid English proficiency was confirmed by his wife. Oral consent was obtained from the patient and his wife before the testing session.

The study was applied in 2014 during a training period at the Razi hospital which aimed at getting acquainted with language pathology matters and more particularly at how aphasia could affect the linguistic aptitude of brain damaged patients. The patient was selected after an ergo therapeutic session where the researcher was present and noted GT's spontaneous use of English at several occasions to communicate with other patients or to respond to the ergo therapeutic specialist. In the following, the tasks will be detailed.

2.2. Tasks

The premorbid proficiency at the English language made of GT a good candidate for examination. Nonetheless, adopting a thorough comprehensive neuropsychological battery to examine the linguistic decay of the patient emanating from PPA was not possible due to practical concerns (mainly evolving around the patient's availability). Thus, GT's access to the lexical semantic system of the two languages (TA vs. English) was tested through a set of picture-naming tasks for which output was required first in TA and then in English. Different semantic categories were set for the testing: Letters (the entire alphabet), Numbers (1-10), Plants (flower, peas, cabbage, potato, onion), Animals (cat, dog, cow, horse, bird, grasshopper, tiger), Body parts (hair, ear, tooth, mouth, nose, hand), Colors (blue, green, red, yellow, orange), Clothes (shoe, dress, trousers).

² MRI : Magnetic resonance imaging

³ MMS: Mini-Mental State (a cognitive test)

The tasks were not time-limited. The patient was free to take the time he needed to reflect before giving his final answer. While not restricting the patient to an exact interval of time we a) avoided stressing him out and b) provided more time to get the target accurate answers. Although the task requirements were not complicated, varied objects (spoon, phone, table, book, car, tractor, house, man) were first administered to the patient to make sure he understood the procedure before getting into the actual target items. The results will be detailed and discussed in the following.

3. *Results and discussion*

The patient answered accurately in the TA Letter naming task with remarkable ease. The same was true in the English Letter naming task with the exception of the vowel 'u' for which more time was needed and the response was clearly doubtful. Concerning the naming of Numbers, TG performed well in both languages. His confidence was beyond questioning. As for the colors, the performance of GT was clearly deficient when compared to the first two categories. He was successful in both languages in one instance only (i.e. blue color). Naming Colors in TA was possible for orange, green, and yellow. For the red color, GT could only find the English name and failed to generate the TA counterpart.

The following task administered to the patient targeted objects belonging to different semantic categories (Body parts, Clothes, Plants, Animals). Despite the fact that the patient was first required to name the thing in the picture in Arabic and then in English, certain answers were uttered spontaneously in English first suggesting the item was first accessed and retrieved from the English lexical store of the patient.

In general terms, producing paraphasias was rare in GT's production. One exception occurred with the 'tooth' picture where he responded using unrelated verbal paraphasia

[toffɜ:h; English: 'apple']. However, it should be noted that the first letter [t] in the TA word is the first letter of the target word in English. Still the number of the shared letters did not confirm to Nickels' (2001) criteria of relatedness which states that at least 50 % of the letters should be shared between the target word and the produced one so it could be considered a phonemic paraphasia. This may be the only instance where the two lexical systems seemed to be co-activated causing a probable overlapping. The actual "overlapping brain activation" of L1 and L2 was evidenced by Mouthon et al., (2013, p. 268). Another rare example of paraphasia occurring in the data was a semantic paraphasia where the nose was named in TA

as [wõm] (English: 'ear'). In the latter instance, GT faced a problem finding the TA name of the nose and he was not able to produce the English name either. It should be noted that circumlocutions were rarely used to help the patient cope with word finding difficulties. The only instance of use occurred with the man picture where GT said during his search for the target name "maybe he is a student" then said [ra:zɪl] (English: 'man'). Afterwards, when the examiner requested the word in English, GT directly responded "he is a man". That was the only instance where a circumlocution in English was produced before the patient could utter the right TA name and the right English one. In specific items, GT found easily the TA name but could not find the English counterpart even after phonological aid. This occurred with dog, bird, grasshopper, trousers, and cabbage. However, two exceptions to this fact occurred. The first was with the dress picture (though after a long time and a repetitive phonological help in which the two letters of the target English word 'dress' were provided). The second item was the potato picture where TA name was directly uttered while the English name was only possible after phonological aid. TA was the only accessible language in 7 cases while English was the only accessible language in one instance only (Red color). In one instance (tooth picture), an unrelated verbal paraphasia in TA was produced before the target TA was uttered and then the English target word was directly stated. In three instances (dog, bird, and dress), the English name was only found after phonological help while the TA was directly uttered. The scarceness of the produced errors fall short of determining specific constraints based on a typically

organized lexico-semantic processing system that distinguished between L1 and L2, which could not clearly reflect any language-specific cognitive processes in error production.

The results show that both L1 and L2 were “affected to a clinically significant degree” like what found Zanini et al. (2011) in the study of a PPA clinical case. More specifically findings suggested a possible dissociation within each language system as well as between both languages. One possible account for differences between L1 and L2 could lie on a category-specificity account (see Capitani et al. (2003) for a thorough review of category-specific semantic deficits). This account entails that the emerging differences resulted from a relative disproportionate knowledge for specific semantic categories compared to others that was more apparent with L2 than with L1. Probable specific neural processes should stand behind the categorical effect being more pronounced in one language system (i.e. English) than in the other (i.e. TA).

Both languages (TA & English) were almost equally preserved when tested with Letters and Numbers. This echoes the reported fact that “Neurophysiologic and neuroimaging studies evidenced a similar cerebral representation of L1 and L2 lexicons both in early and late bilinguals” (Fabbro, 2001, p. 211). However, the claimed similarity did not hold in all circumstances. In categories other than Letters and Numbers, out of 30 item (the piloted items included), GT responded accurately and directly in both languages in 18 instances only. Thus, a possible account for the differences between L1 and L2 at this level probably lies on the difference between both language systems regarding the grammatical gender of nouns. Indeed, Fabbro (2001) noted that “the representation of grammatical aspects of languages seems to be different between the two languages if L2 is acquired after the age of 7, with automatic processes and correctness being lower than those of the native language” (p. 211).

The current study indirectly dealt with some grammatical aspects of the two languages since naming an object in TA necessitates dealing with its grammatical gender

at some point of the cognitive processing mechanism in concordance with the claimed effect of thought on language perception and use evidenced by Boroditsky (2009; 2011), Boroditsky and Schmidt (2000), and Boroditsky et al. (2003). Findings of this study showed that difference between both languages was pronounced in the categories of objects to which a grammatical gender could be assigned in TA (English is a neuter language regarding the grammatical gender aspect of nouns) and not pronounced with categories like Letters and Numbers for which a grammatical gender effect is irrelevant. This finding, thus, supports the probable effect of gender differences on objects perception in different language systems as found Boroditsky and Schmidt (2000), and Boroditsky et al. (2003). The previous works showed that speakers of languages where objects could be grammatically gendered (e.g. 'hand' in TA is feminine vs. 'dog' in TA is masculine; 'hand' and 'dog' are neuter in English) do perceive these objects as receiving feminine or masculine qualities in correspondence to their grammatical gender. If the speaker is influenced by the way s/he perceives an object X this entails that thinking in TA lead to specific cognitive mechanisms including specific routes of knowledge that would differ from those activated while thinking in English to perceive the same object X. As object perception is one stage in a picture-naming task which probes the visual modality then a possible effect of the grammatical gender of objects may have influenced the answers of GT and differentiated between his perceptions for the same object when thinking in a different linguistic code.

The foreign language (English) for which the patient reached a good level of proficiency after leaving several years in America did not show a particular resistance to damage. The comparatively relative spontaneous flow of the mother tongue (Tunisian Arabic dialect) suggested a probable advantage for L1 over English which runs counter claims about the most vulnerability of the first acquired language in case of acute brain damage (Ribot, 1906). This further delineates the nature of the damage affecting language-related neural areas in acute vs. progressive aphasia as well as the nature itself of the involved areas. It, consequently, distinguishes the progressive aphasia effect on the neural

basis of L1/L2 processing from the acute aphasia's basis. However, the patient's spontaneous use of English (L2) in a few cases downgraded the absolute advantage for L1 over L2 and minimizes the importance of the reported differences elsewhere which require further investigations to build solid interpretations.

In effect, the findings of the present case study allow to verify the convergence hypothesis (Green, 2003) which assumes that "the neural substrates of language representations are shared between the languages of a bilingual speaker", and predicts that "neurodegenerative disease should produce parallel deterioration to lexical and grammatical processing in bilingual aphasia" (Druks & Weekes, 2014, p. 578). The differences reported between TA and English performances suggest L2 to be more vulnerable to neurodegenerative brain damage than L1 as partly found Fabbro (2001) in 20% of the studied bilingual aphasics. The hypothesis of parallel deterioration seemed to be at stake compared to the current findings. However, this assumption is far from being conclusive since the present study did not afford sufficient data to compare the difference in the actual deterioration between L1 and L2 and focuses on one detailed aspect of the linguistic aptitude which only used the visual modality. Differences although clearly existed, were not so pronounced to totally reject a possible "parallel deterioration to lexical and grammatical processing in bilingual aphasia" (Druks & Weekes, 2014, p. 578).

Several limitations could have affected the results of this study. Some of these could not have been prevented due to external factors. One major limitation is not considering different sessions for the TA denomination and English denomination tasks. Administering the sessions in different days would have ensured that no priming effect could have helped the patient answering in the English language and could have probably led the differences between L1 and L2 to be more pronounced. Besides, due to practical reasons the testing of the numbers was reduced to the first 10 digits only which could not be as comprehensive as testing the whole alphabet (i.e. for letter naming) to allow for a

fair comparison between both categories. The same applied to the color and clothe categories as well whose representative items were less than other categories.

A final limitation concerns the nature of the pictorial stimuli which was not selected from a normative data base ensuring careful control of various psychological norms. The testing set of pictures was colored pictures downloaded from several commercial websites believed to be clear. The use of Snodgrass and Vanderwart's (1980) set of standardized pictures would have offered more credible results to build upon. Hence, caution is warranted before drawing conclusions on the basis of this modest work. Future studies taking into consideration all of these variables should be helpful to verify the present findings.

4. Implications

The present study could have two implications. First, diagnosing the most defective language in a bilingual aphasic patient is of a paramount importance for clinical concerns. In effect, Kambanaros and Grohmann (2011) noted the importance of similar studies in guiding the "clinical intervention for the patient" as well as developing "therapy strategies that focus on specific characteristics of one or multiple languages" (2011, p. 513).

Second, the present findings could be taken further to suggest implications for foreign language teaching. The reported dissociation between L1 and L2 reinforces their segregation at the anatomical level. Cognitively speaking, the two languages are not conceived nor processed the same way. However, although segregated, interactions between languages occur. One instance of interaction reported in the foreign language learning setting is the phenomenon of negative language transfer usually experienced by new language learners. The problematic effect of negative transfer could originate from the nature of this anatomical segregation. One could possibly suggest that the more the two languages are anatomically segregated the less negative language transfer could occur.

Possibly what defines the borders between L1 and L2 is the way the second language was first introduced to the learner and how the learner experienced it. Thus,

reinforcing this anatomical segregation could hopefully minimize problematic language transfer. Authenticity in language learning experience could probably strengthen the language traces in the brain which will maximize its cognitive segregation and minimize the chances for language transfer to occur. What essentially marks the Tunisian foreign language curriculum design, more particularly in the primary and secondary schools where the first threads of segregations are being sewed, is the lack of authentic exposure to the target new language. This calls for the necessity to reconsider efficient ways in introducing learners to foreign languages while maximizing their contact with the target language in authentic settings.

4. *Conclusion*

The present study aimed to compare L1 and L2 after brain damage in the first stages of Alzheimer. Findings suggested that both languages were affected to variable degrees and that neither of them was particularly preserved nor particularly affected. Nonetheless, specific instances where access to L1 was possible while access to L2 was not occurred relatively more than instances where the opposite was the case. This fact occurred with specific semantic categories more than with others which suggested a categorical effect of semantic knowledge affecting L2 more than L1. Differences revealed between both languages suggested their segregation at the cognitive level which could have important implications if applied to both clinical and teaching fields.

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